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Nazokat B. Abdullaeva,
Lecturer department of History,
Urgench State University
nazokata465@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The question of the role of the Korean diaspora in the socio-economic life of the region, resettled in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, including the Khorezm region in the 30s of the twentieth century, is one of the practically unanalyzed scientific topics. After all, great achievements were achieved with the help of the “kobondi” method of economic production, based on a market economy, which was rejected by a socialist society based only on state ownership of production. However, this method of production was not analyzed in scientific studies of the Soviet period precisely because it did not correspond to the economic ideology of the Soviet regime. From this point of view, this article is devoted to the analysis of this method of production of “kobondi” and the role of the Korean diaspora in the economic life of the Khorezm region.

Index Terms: Koreans, diaspora, deportation, kobondi, kobondya, capitalist system, multiple ownership, seasonal rent, “people's property”, Gurlen, Khanka, Urgench, collective farm, state farm.

Nazokat Baxtiyorovna Abdullaeva,
Urganch davlat universiteti Tarix kafedrası o‘qituvchisi
nazokata465@gmail.com

1940-1980 YILLAR OXIRLARIDA XORAZM VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KOREYS DIASPORASINING ROLI

ANNOTATSIYA

XX asrning 30-yillarida Xorazm viloyatiga ko‘chirib keltirilgan koreyslar diasporasining viloyat ijtimoiy – iqtisodiy hayotida tutgan o‘rni masalasi deyarli tahlil qilinmagan ilmiy mavzulardan biri hisoblanadi. Zero, faqat davlat mulkchiligiga asoslangan sotsialistik jamiyat rad qilgan va bozor iqtisodiyotiga asoslangan “kobondi” xo‘jalik ishlab chiqarish uslubi yordamida juda katta yutuqlarga erishilgan. Ammo, aynan shu sovet hokimiyati iqtisodiy mafkurasiga mos kelmaganligi uchun bu ishlab chiqarish uslubi sovet davri ilmiy tadqiqotlarida tahlil qilinmagan.

Shu jihatdan olganda mazkur maqola ana shu “kobondi” ishlab chiqarish uslubi tahliliga va umuman koreyslar diasporasining Xorazm viloyati xo‘jalik-iqtisodiy hayotidagi tutgan o‘rni masalasi tahliliga bag‘ishlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: koreyslar, diaspora, deportatsiya, kobondi, kobondya, kapitalistik uklad, ko‘pmulkchilik, mavsumiy ijara, “xalq mulki”, Gurlan, Xonqa, Urganch, kolxoz, sovxoz.

Назокат Бахтиёровна Абдуллаева,
Преподаватель кафедры Истории
Ургенчского государственного университета
nazokata465@gmail.com

РОЛЬ КОРЕЙСКОЙ ДИАСПОРЫ В РАЗВИТИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ В КОНЦЕ 1940-1980-Х ГГ.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Вопрос о роли корейской диаспоры в социально-экономической жизни региона, переселенной в Казахстан и Узбекистан, в том числе Хорезмскую область в 30-е годы XX века, является одной из практически не анализируемых научных тем. Ведь большие достижения были достигнуты с помощью способа экономического производства «kobondi», основанном на рыночной экономике, который был отвергнут основанным только на государственной собственности производства социалистическим обществом. Однако этот способ производства не анализировался в научных исследованиях советского периода именно потому, что он не соответствовал экономической идеологии советской власти. С этой точки зрения данная статья посвящена анализу этого способа производства «kobondi» и роли корейской диаспоры в экономической жизни Хорезмской области.

Ключевые слова: Корейцы, диаспора, депортация, kobondi, kobondya, капиталистический строй, многовладение, сезонная аренда, «народная собственность», Гурлен, Ханка, Ургенч, колхоз, совхоз.

INTRODUCTION:

The issue of the role of the Korean diaspora, which relocated to the Khorezm region in the 1930s, in the socio-economic life of the region is one of the scarcely analyzed scientific topics. In particular, the achievements of the Korean diaspora in the agricultural sector of the region were recognized worldwide at that time. However, these achievements were not impartially assessed in Soviet literature and were instead interpreted as the successes of the socialist society. Notably, the production method used by Koreans, known as "kobondi," was not scientifically analyzed even in specialized literature. Under the dominance of the socialist society's ideology, which was based solely on state ownership, the kobondi production method was considered a defect of the capitalist society. Consequently, this method was not accepted in practice by the Soviet government and was not scientifically analyzed at all during those times.

In this respect, this article is dedicated to the analysis of the kobondi production method and, in general, the role of the Korean diaspora in the economic life of the Khorezm region. The declassification of many archival funds and the increase in oral history data indicate the need for a broader and, most importantly, scientifically objective approach to this topic. However, this article does not discuss Korean state farms (sovkhozes) and collective farms (kolkhozes) where Koreans formed the majority of the population, such as the Al-Khwarizmi state farm in the Khanka district and the Kommunist collective farm in the Gurlan district. These Korean state and collective farms were themselves famous as a unique phenomenon during the Soviet era and constitute a separate subject of research.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The history and culture of the Korean diaspora's settlement in Khorezm have not been sufficiently studied as a separate research topic to date. Most local and foreign works on the subject of Korea were published during the former Soviet era. Since the Korean diaspora in the Soviet state

was viewed as a single ethnic group, many studies were dedicated to Soviet Koreans. However, the empirical materials of these studies were based on Koreans living in specific regions (for instance, Uzbekistan or Kazakhstan). For this reason, and also because the majority of Soviet Koreans lived in Central Asia, many titles in Korean studies are dedicated to Central Asian Koreans, even though these works often focus on Koreans in particular republics, such as Kazakhstan or Uzbekistan.

Various aspects of the history, social life, and culture of Koreans living in the regions of Uzbekistan, including the kobondi farming method specifically related to the Korean diaspora during the period of Soviet rule, are reflected in the works of researchers such as V.S. Khan [1], B. Kim [2], G. Lee [3] D. Men [4], and A. Rakhmonqulova[5]. Taking all this existing literature into account highlights the need to develop issues related to the role of the Korean diaspora in the development of agricultural sectors in the Khorezm oasis in the context of applying programs that reflect the social conditions of diasporas in Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The article employs scientific research methods such as systematization, historical-comparative analysis, generalization of historical data, and the principle of objectivity.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS:

The role of the Korean diaspora in the development of industrial and agricultural sectors in the region is highlighted. As previously mentioned, when Koreans were relocated to the territories of Uzbekistan, the level of industrial development in the republic was low. With the policy of industrialization starting in 1927, industrial sectors were still forming and, by the late 1930s, had not yet met the required standards. Additionally, since Koreans were mainly settled in rural and largely undeveloped areas, they primarily engaged in agriculture in Uzbekistan during the 1940s and 1960s. In 1959, 44,112 of the 138,453 Koreans in the Uzbek SSR lived in cities, meaning that approximately 32% of Koreans of Uzbekistan resided in urban areas[6]. However, most urban Koreans were still involved in agricultural activities[7]. In the countryside, Koreans typically formed their villages, which became known colloquially as Korean collective farms (kolkhozes).

Overall, the role of the Korean diaspora in agricultural development was unparalleled, and they achieved great success in this field. Especially during the war years, Korean kolkhozes played a crucial role in meeting the needs of the front. The labor achievements of Korean representatives in agriculture during and after the war were significant; while 135 individuals in Uzbekistan were awarded the title of Hero of Socialist Labor, nearly a thousand members of the Korean diaspora were honored with high state orders and medals[8]. No other ethnic group in the multi-ethnic USSR could boast such achievements. In this regard, Koreans living in the Khorezm region also achieved remarkable success in agriculture. For instance, four ethnic Koreans from the Khorezm region were awarded the highest title of Hero of Socialist Labor. In 1950, two individuals from the Stalin (later Kommunist, now Vazir) kolkhoz in Gurlan district, Nyu Kvansen and Yugay German, received this title. In 1966, N. Pak, a brigadier from the same Kommunist kolkhoz, and in 1973, N.V. Kim, who had long led the Al-Khwarizmi state farm in Khanka district, were also honored for their achievements in agriculture[9].

Crop yields in Korean state and collective farms were significantly higher than those in other kolkhozes and sovkhoses. For example, members of the Kommunist Kolkhoz in Gurlan district harvested 60–80 quintals of rice per hectare. This figure was not only higher than the average in the Khorezm region but also exceeded the averages across the former USSR. In contrast, rice yields in other kolkhozes in Uzbekistan ranged from 24-27 quintals per hectare. One of the most famous rice varieties today, the "Laser" variety, gained worldwide fame largely due to the efforts of Nikolay Kim, the leader of the Al-Khwarizmi state farm in Khanka district[10]. The high yields in Korean kolkhozes and sovkhoses were achieved through rational use of every inch of land and extremely hard work.

Additionally, Koreans achieved high yields not only in traditional rice cultivation but also in other crops, such as string, cotton, sugar beets, watermelons, corn, and onions. Koreans even surpassed Uzbek farmers in cotton cultivation, a new crop for Koreans in Uzbekistan. Cotton yields in Korean kolkhozes reached 40–45% per hectare, while those in Uzbek kolkhozes and sovkhoses

managed only 25–30%[11]. By the 1950s, Korean kolkhozes had established dominance in string cultivation, with yields of 70–80 quintals per hectare compared to just 10–15 quintals in Uzbek kolkhozes[12].

Overall, the achievements of Korean kolkhozes and sovkhozes served as a model for increasing agricultural productivity across Central Asia and Kazakhstan. However, despite global recognition of the Korean diaspora's achievements in agriculture, Soviet literature did not impartially assess these successes, interpreting them instead as accomplishments of the socialist society. The kobondi production method used by Koreans was not scientifically analyzed, even in specialized laboratories. Under the dominance of an ideology based solely on state ownership, the kobondi method was viewed as a defect of capitalist society. As a result, it was neither accepted by the Soviet government in practice nor analyzed scientifically. This section of the research focuses specifically on the analysis of the kobondi production method and farm structure.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS:

In general, even during the era when the socialist society, which rejected private ownership and was based solely on state ownership, was flourishing, the Koreans of Uzbekistan achieved great success in their economic lives using the kobondi production method. This method, based on market economy principles, was rejected by the socialist society. However, this production method was not analyzed in Soviet-era scientific research. In this context, the Korean diaspora living in the region introduced many innovations and crop cultivation technologies in the agricultural sector. Analyzing these contributions in detail across different districts of the region is of urgent importance.

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Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
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